

Physical Fitness of Students under the Influence of Targeted Volleyball Training

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Annotation:

Volleyball is a dynamic team sport that has gained wide popularity all over the world. This game requires not only physical fitness, but also strategic thinking, teamwork and high concentration. Volleyball has become not only a professional sport, but also an integral part of the leisure time of millions of people, from amateurs to world-class athletes. During the study, an analysis of scientific research was carried out on the problem of improving the physical fitness of student youth in higher education institutions using sports-oriented training. A study of the strength indicators of physical fitness of students (dead-endurance, strength endurance - flexion, extension of arms from a lying position, maintaining an angle in a hang) was conducted with senior students. According to the results of the studied indicators, a certain increase in results occurred.

Keywords: students, volleyball, sports orientation, health, physical qualities, physical fitness.

Introduction. In the National Doctrine of Education Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, physical culture and sports are an important area of social policy of civil society, an effective means of organizing leisure and quality of life, achieving a health and educational effect. Taking this into account, higher professional education faces the task of training a qualified specialist to ensure satisfactory physical and mental health of student youth. Schools and universities do everything possible to ensure that the younger generation grows up healthy, comprehensively and harmoniously developed. And a significant role in this belongs to the physical fitness of student youth [2, 3, 5].

Physical fitness of a person is one of the criteria of health, and in the practice of physical education of students in universities - the main criterion of its effectiveness. Therefore, the methodology for organizing and conducting physical education classes in universities requires further improvement, in particular the development and scientific substantiation of new ways to improve the quality of the

physical education process [1, 4, 7]. There is a need to search for new forms and methods of conducting classes, organizing the educational process [6, 8]. We see ensuring the physical fitness of students in the implementation of the sports direction of study groups, which, as experience and analysis of recent studies show, have higher rates of physical and functional fitness compared to students who studied according to the general physical training program. Most often, in groups with a sports focus, elements of sports games, types of gymnastics, and other sports are used [9, 18]. The advantage of this form of organizing classes is a high emotional background and the ability to take into account the interests of students. In achieving the main goal in physical education, which is to acquire an optimal state of physical health for different segments of the population, scientists are inclined to develop original methods that have experimentally proven the effectiveness of teaching methods for general students of universities with a sports profile, taking into account the sports specializations of students and the level of development of motor skills, which contributes to a better assimilation of the technique of playing volleyball in accordance with the credit-modular training system [10, 14]. Pedagogical technologies for fostering a culture of interaction between teachers and students have been developed and experimentally tested [15, 16]. An unsatisfactory state of the indicators of somatic health, physical development and motor fitness of students was established, the positive influence of various sports-oriented means on the functional state of students was confirmed, a method for correcting the physical fitness and functional state of the body of students of technical universities was developed, and it was shown that the level of fitness according to the scale of state tests corresponds to the assessment of "average" and "below average" [11, 12, 17].

Literature review. Physical education in higher education institutions should promote health and development of motor skills. To solve these problems, it is necessary to study the level of physical fitness of students and, based on the results obtained, take into account individual characteristics and conduct effective physical education classes. The fact of the existence of a close relationship between the health of young people and the organization and methodology of physical education is confirmed in the works of many leading scientists (V. K. Balsevich, V. A. Zaporozhan, A. G. Sukharev, T. Yu. Krutsevich, and others). In today's conditions, one of the most accessible and effective means of disease prevention and improving mental and physical performance is physical education.

Methodology. In accordance with the goals and objectives of the study, the following generally accepted methods were used: theoretical analysis of domestic and foreign scientific sources, pedagogical methods (formative pedagogical experiment), mathematical and statistical methods of data processing.

Physical education and sports are an integral part of the educational process of children, youth and the full life of the adult population of our country and should be based on strengthening physical and mental health, an integrated approach to the formation of mental and motor qualities of the individual, improving physical and mental preparedness for an active life. professional activity on the principles of an individual approach, priority of health orientation, wide use of various methods and forms of physical improvement [7].

Most students have insufficient development of general professionally important qualities. This significantly slows down the assimilation of the motor components of the chosen specialty and professional adaptation. One of the main reasons that negatively affect the development of body functions, ensuring adaptation to educational and industrial activities, is a sedentary lifestyle, because it is known that physical activity increases the non-specific resistance of the body to the negative effects of cooling, overheating, radiation, and the volume of information [4].

Particularly noteworthy are first-year students, who experience the process of adaptation of the body to new living conditions, when the usual rhythm of learning and lifestyle at school passes to

new activities at universities, where there are a large number of different factors that load the intellectual sphere and motor activity of students. Recently, a low level of physical fitness has been observed among students entering the first year of university [2].

Numerous data show that targeted influence through physical education allows achieving a certain effect in strengthening health. However, the task is not only to use optimal physical education tools depending on age, gender, initial level of health and ability to work. It is important, by monitoring the effectiveness of their impact on the body, to make adjustments to physical education programs depending on the morphological and functional state [9].

Results. The Department of Sports Management carries out targeted work with student youth to improve their physical fitness by means of physical culture and sports. At the beginning of the 1st and 2nd semesters, all faculties teach a 60-hour lecture course on volleyball. Teachers pay special attention to the level of students' physical fitness for physical education classes.

At Termez State University, volleyball classes were held using an original technique to improve the general physical fitness of student youth. The content of the technique consisted of using simple and accessible sports-oriented means – “Volleyball”, taking into account the age group, the level of physical fitness of male students and the time of the lesson in the daily routine.

To determine the effectiveness of the original technique, a study was conducted of some strength indicators of students' physical fitness (strength, strength endurance - flexion, extension of arms from a prone position, holding an angle in a hang) with senior students. Strength endurance was determined by the indicators of push-ups from the floor and the time of the angle of the angle in hanging on the horizontal bar (keeping the legs at an angle of at least 75°).

When distributing students into control and experimental groups, we took into account their interests and inclinations when choosing a sports focus for physical education classes. Students who did not show interest in sports-focused classes were assigned to the general physical training group and made up the control group of 25 people. The experimental group consisted of 25 students who expressed a desire to play volleyball in the sports focus “Volleyball”. Classes in these groups were held six hours a week during the academic year.

Students in the control and experimental groups underwent testing of the main indicators of physical fitness in early October (the beginning of the experiment) and late May (the end of the experiment).

The increase in each of the data over the year was significantly higher for the experimental group students compared to the control group. Thus, if the first-year young men of the experimental group showed a 21.22% increase in the strength indicator over the first year of study at universities and physical education classes with a sports focus, then for their peers from the control group it was 16.15%. It should be noted that the dynamics of strength endurance indicators maintains the same trend. For the guys from the experimental group, the increase in the push-up indicator over the year of study at the university was 36.7%, for the students from the control group - 22.34%. The indicator for holding an angle in a hang over the first year of study at universities increased by 13% for the guys in the experimental group, and by 11.3% for their peers from the control group. Consequently, the study showed that sports-oriented classes with elements of volleyball had a positive effect on the strength indicators under study.

Conclusions. The results of the study showed that volleyball classes with a sports focus and elements of volleyball had a positive effect on the strength indicators under study: the increase in indicators at the end of the experiment in the experimental group was greater than in the control group (class strength - by 5.07%, flexion-extension) of the arms in support - by 14.38%, holding an

angle in a hang - by 1.7%). Consequently, the introduction of sports-oriented classes into the educational process contributes to the improvement of the general physical fitness of students.

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